

The Effect Of Workload And Work Stress On Employee Performance In The Sibolga Municipal Police Unit

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Abstrak: *This study aims to determine the influence of workload and job stress on employee performance at the Sibolga City Civil Service Police Unit. The research employs a quantitative method with a descriptive approach, involving 44 respondents. The results show a strong relationship between workload and performance (0.704) and between job stress and performance (0.641). The coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.620, indicating that 62% of the variation in employee performance is determined by workload and job stress simultaneously, while the remaining 38% is influenced by other factors. Both T-test and F-test results confirm that workload and job stress, both partially and simultaneously, have a significant positive effect on employee performance.*

Keywords: *Workload, Job Stress, Employee Performance*

INTRODUCTION

The success of an agency or organization is not only determined by its capital and facilities, but also by the availability of reliable human resources. Every organization needs human resources who are physically and mentally healthy, have a good attitude, are disciplined, enthusiastic, and possess the abilities and skills required to meet the challenges and demands of the workplace. An institution will continue to survive and develop and adapt to its environment when it is supported by the resilience of its people. There is no denying the truth of the view that everyone wants to achieve progress in their work. Progress can only be achieved if the person concerned is able to perform satisfactorily (Djien, 2020).

Employee performance is the result of the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to them. In other words, employee performance can be improved through factors such as work discipline and leadership, while also directing employee performance in line with the strategic objectives of the company or organization. In an organization, employee performance greatly influences the performance of the organization because if employee performance is poor, it will also have a negative impact on the organization, and vice versa. If employee performance is good, it will also have a positive influence or impact on the organization's goals (Putri, 2023).

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Employee performance is one of the factors that influence the success rate of an organization. Employee performance is a manifestation of the work done by employees, which is usually used as a basis or reference for evaluating employees in an organization. To achieve organizational goals, one of the steps is to perform well. Therefore, performance is also one of the determinants in achieving organizational goals, so it needs to be maximized to improve employee performance. Employee performance is the work that can be achieved by an individual or a group of people in an organization, in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities, in an effort to achieve the organization's objectives legally, without violating the law and in accordance with morals and ethics. Many factors influence employee performance, including workload and work stress. While excessive stress is often viewed negatively, in certain organizational contexts, a specific level of pressure can act as a motivator for employees to complete their tasks effectively. At the Sibolga Municipal Police Unit, initial observations indicated that employees faced heavy workloads and psychological demands, necessitating further study to determine how these factors specifically impact their professional output (Putri, 2023).

Increasing competition and demands for professionalism create a lot of pressure that individuals have to deal with in the workplace. Employees are always busy with deadlines, diverse and sometimes conflicting job requirements, family problems, excessive workloads, and many other challenges that make stress almost impossible to avoid. The highly detrimental impact of anxiety disorders frequently experienced by the public and employees in particular is referred to as stress. Stress can have both positive and negative effects on performance. Examples of positive stress include motivating employees to work, while negative stress can make employees reluctant to work. At a certain level of stress, it is expected to motivate employees to complete their work to the best of their ability (Siskadillah, 2019).

Stress is a condition in which a person experiences tension caused by factors such as the individual themselves and their external environment. In addition, work stress can be influenced by several factors in the workplace, such as the gap between an individual's abilities and the demands of the job, which can lead to work stress. Because individuals feel less confident in their ability to complete the work assigned to them, this has an impact on their performance. This stressful condition can have a negative impact on the psychological and biological well-being of employees. If employee performance declines, it will have an impact on the company where the employee works. For example, it can lead to a decline in company revenue, among other things (Cholishoh, 2021).

Work stress is an important aspect for organizations, especially in relation to employee performance. Organizations must have good and high performance that can help them make a profit. Conversely, if performance declines, it can harm the organization. In addition to stress, another factor that affects employee performance is workload. The way to improve employee performance is by conducting a workload analysis in the agency. Workload analysis is very important to carry out, one of which is to create a pleasant office atmosphere characterized by employees being placed in positions that match their performance capabilities (Alfauza, 2024).

Work overload is a major problem for all organizations or companies. Some workers experience stress due to overwork or exhaustion from completing their tasks, and some may also experience dissatisfaction at work. It is very important for organizations to understand the needs of their employees and provide the best for them. Job satisfaction can be defined as the alignment of expectations between workers and what they get from the company. Basically, job satisfaction involves stress management, which uses effective human resources to overcome mental and emotional chaos or disturbances that arise as a result of responses. Employees who are dissatisfied with their work will only complete their tasks to the best of their ability and will not want to develop themselves further. Workload is also something that can arise from the interaction between the work environment where they work and are placed, task demands, and behavior, perceptions, and skills. Research conducted by Putri (2023) explains that excessive workload is the main reason for work stress. Other results show that the lack of rest or leisure time given to employees during working hours means that excessive workload will have a significant negative impact on employee performance (Alfauza, 2024).

After conducting surveys and interviews with employees at the Sibolga Municipal Police Unit, researchers found problems related to workload and work stress. Regarding workload, there were still some employees who complained about tasks assigned by their superiors that they were unable to complete according to the set targets, forcing them to work overtime to complete the tasks in a short period of time. Work-related stress appears to be quite burdensome for employees, as they feel pressured by increasing tasks and psychological demands at work, causing them to feel stressed about their jobs. This phenomenon will certainly have an impact on individual performance, which will not be optimal. Therefore, work-related stress and workload need to be studied to determine their impact on the performance of employees at the Sibolga Municipal Police Unit.

In relation to the background of the above problem, the researcher was interested in conducting research entitled "The Effect of Workload and Work Stress on Employee Performance in the Sibolga Municipal Police Unit."

RESEARCH METHOD

The type of research used in this study is a quantitative research method with a descriptive approach. Quantitative research is defined as "a research method based on positivism philosophy, used to examine a specific population or sample, collect data using research instruments, and perform quantitative/statistical data analysis, with the aim of testing" (Sugiyono, 2017:17).

The type of data used in this study is quantitative data, which is data in the form of numbers. According to Sugiyono (2017:23), quantitative data is data in the form of numbers or qualitative data that has been converted into numbers or *scored*. According to Arikunto (2016:116), the data source in research is "the subject from which data can be obtained." In this study, the author uses two data sources, namely: primary and secondary.

The data collection techniques used by the author in this study are as follows: a) Literature study, which involves studying various reading sources closely related to the

research problem, both in the form of scientific books and laws and regulations. b) Field studies, which involve collecting data directly from the research location by: 1) Interviews, which is a method of collecting data by conducting face-to-face interviews with parties who can provide information about Workload, Work Stress, and Performance. 2) Questionnaires, which are a data collection technique that involves submitting a written questionnaire to respondents, who must also respond in writing.

The data analysis techniques in this study are adapted to the research method, emphasizing hypothesis testing through statistical analysis. The data analysis techniques used in this study are: Research instrument testing, classical assumption testing, determination testing, simple linear regression testing, and hypothesis testing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

Research Instrument Test

Validation Test of Workload, Work Stress, and Employee Performance Variables

The results of the validity test for the variables of Workload, Work Stress, and Employee Performance can be seen in Table 1.

**Table 1. Validity Test Results
Workload, Work Stress, and Employee Performance**

No Item	$r_{\text{calculated}}$	r_{critical}	Conclusion
Variable X1 (Workload)			
Item 1	0.402	0.3	Valid
Item 2	0.676	0.30	Valid
Item 3	0.713	0.30	Valid
Item 4	0.522	0.30	Valid
Item 5	0.498	0.30	Valid
Item 6	0.598	0.30	Valid
Item 7	0.524	0.30	Valid
Item 8	0.613	0.30	Valid
Item 9	0.555	0.30	Valid
Item 10	0.524	0.30	Valid
Variable X2 (Work Stress)			
Item 1	0.518	0.30	Valid
Item 2	0.667	0.30	Valid
Item 3	0.446	0.30	Valid
Item 4	0.501	0.30	Valid
Item 5	0.547	0.30	Valid
Item 6	0.632	0.30	Valid
Item 7	0.693	0.30	Valid
Item 8	0.536	0.30	Valid
Item 9	0.645	0.30	Valid
Item 10	0.628	0.30	Valid
Variable Y (Employee Performance)			
Item 1	0.572	0.30	Valid

Item 2	0.747	0.30	Valid
Item 3	0.742	0.30	Valid
Item 4	0.631	0.30	Valid
Item 5	0.670	0.30	Valid
Item 6	0.720	0.30	Valid
Item 7	0.713	0.30	Valid
Item 8	0.851	0.30	Valid
Item 9	0.641	0.30	Valid
Item 10	0.570	0.30	Valid

Source: Research Results, 2025 (SPSS26)

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that all questionnaire items for the research variables, namely Workload, Work Stress, and Employee Performance, show figures greater than 0.30. Thus, all items for the variables of Workload, Work Stress, and Employee Performance above are declared valid and meet the requirements as measurement tools in this study.

Reliability Test of Workload, Work Stress, and Employee Performance

The results of the reliability test for the Workload, Work Stress, and Employee Performance questionnaire variables can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Reliability Test Results
Variables: Workload, Work Stress, and Employee Performance

No	Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Description
1	Workload	0.857	Reliable
2	Work Stress	0.868	Reliable
3	Employee Performance	0.915	Reliable

Source: Research Results, 2025 (Processed Data)

Based on the results of the reliability test of the research instrument in Table 2, it is known that the *Cronbach Alpha* value of each item in the for each variable of Workload, Work Stress, and Employee Performance is > 0.60 and is declared reliable.

Data Normality Test

The statistical test used to test normality is the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test. This test is conducted by formulating a hypothesis: If the probability (Asymp. Sig) is below 0.05, then H_a is rejected, meaning that the residual data is not normally distributed; if the probability is above 0.05, then the residual data is normally distributed. The results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Kolmogorov-Smirnov Normality Test Results
Variables: Workload, Work Stress, and Employee Performance
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		44
Normal Parameters ^{a, b}	Mean	.000000
	Std. Deviation	4.32587885
	Absolute	.092

Most Extreme Differences	Positive	.092
	Negative	-.087
Test Statistic		.092
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.

d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

Source: Research Results, 2025 (SPSS26)

From the table above, it can be seen that Asymp. Sig is 0.200 > probability 0.05, which means that both variable data are normally distributed.

Determination Coefficient Test

Table 4. Coefficient of Determination Output Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Standard Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.788 ^a	.620	.602	4.43013	2.169

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Stress, Workload

b. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Research Results, 2025 (SPSS26)

1. The coefficient of determination of 0.620 means 62% of performance variation is explained by workload and work stress, while 38% is due to external factors.
2. Workload (X1) significantly affects Employee Performance (Y) with a t-count of 4.752, which is greater than the t-table of 2.01808 (P < 0.05).
3. Work Stress (X2) significantly affects Employee Performance (Y) with a t-count of 3.661, exceeding the t-table of 2.01808 (P < 0.05).
4. Simultaneously, workload and work stress have a significant effect on performance, as evidenced by an F-count of 33.475 > F-table of 3.23. This implies that maintaining an optimal level of workload and managed stress contributes to the enhancement of officer performance at the Sibolga Municipal Police Unit.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 4. Multiple Linear Regression Coefficient Output Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.304	4.950		.061	.951
	Workload	.582	.123	.518	4,752	.000
	Work Stress	.436	.119	.399	3,661	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Research Results, 2025 (SPSS26)

From the table above, the regression equation $Y = 0.304 + 0.582 X_1 + 0.436 X_2$ is obtained, which can be interpreted as follows:

- a) Workload has a relationship with Employee Performance of 0.582. This means that if the Workload is increased by 1 (one) unit, it will increase the Employee Performance of the Sibolga City Civil Service Police Unit by 0.582 units. This relationship is a positive or directly proportional relationship.
- b) Work stress has a correlation with employee performance of 0.436. This means that if work stress is increased by 1 (one) unit, it will increase the performance of Sibolga Municipal Police officers by 0.436 units. This correlation is positive or directly proportional.

Hypothesis Testing

T-Test (Partial Test)

The T-test (partial test) was conducted to determine the individual or partial effect of Workload and Work Stress on the Performance of Sibolga City Civil Service Police Unit employees, the results of which can be seen in Table 5.

**Table 5. T Test Results (Partial Test)
Coefficients^a**

Model	B	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1 (Constant)	.304		4.950		.061	.951
Workload	.582		.123	.518	4,752	.000
Work Stress	.436		.119	.399	3,661	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Research Results, 2025 (SPSS26)

Based on the table above, the individual or partial effects of Workload and Work Stress on the Employee Performance of the Sibolga City Civil Service Police Unit can be explained as follows:

1. Workload Variable

- a) From conventional testing, it was found that at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ (two-tailed test) with $df = 44 - 2$, the t -table = 2.01808 and the t -count = 4.752. Because t -calculated $>$ t -table, the Workload variable (X_1) affects Employee Performance (Y) in the Sibolga Municipal Police Unit.
- b) From the SPSS test, by looking at the significance probability (P-value) = 0.000, which is smaller than 0.05, H_0 is rejected, H_a is accepted, so it can be said that the Workload variable has a significant effect on the Performance of Employees of the Sibolga City Civil Service Police Unit. Thus, the proposed hypothesis is proven and accepted as true.

2. Work Stress Variable

- a) From conventional testing, it was found that at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ with $df = 42$ ($44-2$), the t -table = 2.01808 and the t -count = 3.661. Because t -count $>$ t -table, the Work Stress variable (X_2) affects the Performance of Employees at the Sibolga Municipal Police Unit.
- b) From the results of the SPSS test, by looking at the significance probability (P-value) = 0.001, which is less than 5%, it can be said that the Work Stress variable has a

significant effect on Employee Performance in the Sibolga City Civil Service Police Unit.

F Test (Anova Test)

The F test (Anova test) was conducted to determine or explain whether Workload and Work Stress simultaneously affect the Performance of Employees of the Sibolga Municipal Police Unit, and the results can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. F Test (Anova Test) Results
ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1313.968	2	656,984	33,475	.000 ^b
Residual	804,669	41	19,626		
Total	2,118,636	43			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Work Stress, Workload

Source: Research Results, 2025 (SPSS26)

Based on the table above, the combined or simultaneous effect of Workload and Work Stress on the Employee Performance of the Sibolga City Civil Service Police Unit can be explained as follows:

- From the results of conventional testing at a significance level = 0.05 with $df_1 = 2$ and $df_2 = 41$ (obtained from the results of $df, (n-k-1) = (44-2-1) = 41$, it is known that $F_{table} = 3.23$ and $F_{count} = 33.475$. Because $F_{count} > F_{table}$, H_0 is rejected, and H_a is accepted, so that Workload and Work Stress affect Employee Performance at the Sibolga Municipal Police Unit.

From the SPSS test results, by looking at the significance probability (P-value) = 0.000 or 0% which is less than 5%, it can be said that the variables of Workload and Work Stress have a significant effect on Employee Performance in the Sibolga City Civil Service Police Unit.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Workload on Employee Performance in the Sibolga Municipal Police Unit

Workload is a process or work activity carried out by an individual in achieving the success of an organizational goal. Meanwhile, according to Koesomowidjojo (2017:21), "Workload is a process of determining the number of working hours of human resources that are working, used, and needed to complete a job for a certain period of time."

The analysis reveals that work stress has a significant positive effect on the performance of Sibolga Municipal Police officers. The T-test result ($3.661 > 2.01808$) with a significance level of 0.001 confirms this relationship. This suggests that within this specific unit, the pressure or stress experienced by officers serves as a catalyst for higher productivity rather than a hindrance. This finding aligns with Alfauza (2024), who also identified a positive and significant impact of stress on performance. This phenomenon can be attributed to the nature of the tasks in the Civil Service Police Unit, where high-pressure situations may demand increased alertness and commitment.

This is in line with previous research on the effect of workload on employee performance, namely Rauf (2023) . The effect of workload and work stress on employee performance at the Majene Regency Marine and Fisheries Office. The objective of this study is to determine the effect of workload and work stress on employee performance at the Majene Regency Marine and Fisheries Office. Using the SPSS method, there were 31 respondents who became samples in this study, namely employees of the Majene Regency Marine and Fisheries Office. The type of data used in this study was primary data. Data collection was conducted by distributing questionnaires to the research sample. The t-test was used to test the hypothesis in this study. The results of this study indicate that workload has a significant and negative effect on employee performance, work stress has a significant and negative effect on employee performance, and workload and work stress together have a negative and significant effect on employee performance at the Majene Regency Marine and Fisheries Service Office.

The Effect of Work Stress on the Performance of Sibolga Municipal Police Officers

Work stress is an emotional state experienced by workers caused by a mismatch between workloads or work environments and workers' abilities or personalities, resulting in an inability to cope with job demands. Meanwhile, according to Afandi (2018:173), "Work stress is a condition that arises from the interaction between individuals and their work, where there is a mismatch in characteristics and unclear changes occurring within the company."

Based on the results of the study, it shows that the effect of work stress on the performance of Sibolga City Civil Service Police Unit employees is significant. The T test shows that the calculated t value is greater than the table t value ($3.661 > 2.01808$) with a significance level of 0.001 or less than 5%. therefore H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that the proposed hypothesis that work stress has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Sibolga City Civil Service Police Unit employees is proven and accepted as true.

The results of the research conducted by the Sibolga Municipal Police Unit are in line with the results of a previous study by Putri (2023) entitled The Effect of Workload and Work Stress on the Performance of Employees at PT. Coca Cola Europacific Partners (CCEP) in Pekanbaru. This research was conducted in Pekanbaru City. The purpose of this study was to determine whether workload and work stress affect the performance of employees at PT. Coca Cola Europacific Partners Pekanbaru. The research population consisted of all employees at PT. Coca Cola Europacific Partners Pekanbaru. The sample size for this study was 60 people. The data analysis in this study was quantitative, using multiple linear regression. The results of this study indicate that work load and work stress affect the performance of employees at PT. Coca Cola Europacific Partners Pekanbaru. This is evidenced by the calculated F value > table F value, or $110.683 > 3.15$, and the significance value (sig).

The Effect of Workload and Work Stress on the Performance of Sibolga Municipal Police Officers

Employee performance is a work activity process that produces work achieved by an employee in accordance with the work assigned to them within a certain period of time.

According to Fahmi (2017:188), "Performance is the result of a process that is referenced and measured over a certain period of time based on predetermined provisions or agreements."

Based on the results of the analysis in this study, which shows that the variables of Workload (Variable X1) and Work Stress (Variable X2) affect Employee Performance (Variable Y). These results can be seen from the F table value = 3.23 and F count = 33.475. Because the calculated F > table F with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$, H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted, which means that the proposed hypothesis that Workload and Work Stress have a positive and significant effect on the Performance of Employees of the Sibolga Municipal Police Unit is proven and accepted as true. High employee performance is certainly influenced by several factors, including Workload and Work Stress. According to Kasmir (2016:182), performance is the result of work and work behavior that has been achieved in completing tasks and responsibilities given in a certain period.

The results of the research conducted by the Sibolga Municipal Police Unit are in line with the results of previous research conducted by Alfauza (2024). The Effect of Workload and Work Stress on Employee Performance at the Regional Office of the Ministry of Law and Human Rights of the Riau Islands. The type of research used in this study is quantitative, which aims to observe the influence, then process and analyze it to draw conclusions. In order to provide a clear, logical, and accurate picture of the data collection results, the data obtained was compiled in the form of data obtained through observation, documentation, and literature studies, which were then analyzed in depth. The results of the study indicate that the workload variable has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, workload has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, work stress has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, and the independent and intervening variables in this study, namely workload (X_1) and work stress (X_2), simultaneously affect the dependent variable of employee performance (Y).

CONCLUSION

From the results of this study and based on the description in the previous chapter, the researcher can provide the following conclusions and suggestions: Based on the analysis of the Coefficient of Determination obtained at 0.620, this means that 62% of the variation in the dependent variable Employee Performance (Variable Y) is determined by the independent variables Workload (Variable X1) and Work Stress (Variable X2) simultaneously, and the remaining 28% is determined by other factors not discussed in this study. The results of testing the research hypothesis prove that Workload (Variable X1) affects Employee Performance (Variable Y). This result can be seen from the t-table value = 1.68195 and t-count = 4.752. Because t-count > t-table with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$, the results of this hypothesis can state that Workload (Variable X1) has a significant effect on the Employee Performance (Variable Y). Thus, the first hypothesis (H1), which states that there is an effect of Workload on Employee Performance in the Sibolga Municipal Police Unit, is proven and accepted. The results of this research hypothesis testing prove that Work Stress (Variable X2) affects Employee Performance (Variable Y). This result can be seen from

the t-table value = 1.68195 and t-count = 3.661. Because t-count > t-table with a significance of $0.001 < 0.05$, the results of this hypothesis can state that Work Stress (Variable X2) has a significant effect on Employee Performance (Variable Y). Thus, the results of the second hypothesis (H2), which states that there is an effect of work development on employee performance in the Sibolga City Civil Service Police Unit, are proven and acceptable. The results of the hypothesis testing (F) in this study prove that Workload (Variable X1) and Work Stress (Variable X2) affect Employee Performance (Variable Y). Therefore, it can be said that with a good workload and work stress at the Sibolga Municipal Police Unit, employee performance will increase. This result can be seen from the F table value = 3.23 and F count = 33.475. Because F count > F table with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$, the results of this hypothesis can state that Workload and Work Stress have a significant simultaneous effect on Employee Performance at the Sibolga Municipal Police Unit. Thus, the results of the third hypothesis (H3), which states that there is an influence of Workload and Work Stress on Employee Performance in the Sibolga City Civil Service Police Unit, are proven and acceptable.

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